

Perceived Social Support and Psychological Well-being in Diverse Parenting Contexts

Kavita Thapa¹ and Anu Sharma²

*Department of Psychology, M.B Govt.P. G College, Haldwani, Kumaun University, Nainital, Uttarakhand¹
Special Educator, D.A.V Public School, Sector-10A, Gurugram, Haryana²*

The current study investigated the perceived social support and psychological well-being among parents of children who have developmental disabilities and those parents who have normally developing children. The study was carried out utilizing a descriptive methodology. Through purposive sampling 76 parents were selected to take part in the study. The findings showed that the two groups differed significantly on psychological well-being and perceived social support. Moreover, a positive correlation was noted between the perceived social support and psychological well-being among both groups.

Keywords: Social support, psychological health, disability, children, developmental, standard, differential

The arrival of a new-born adds joy to the family. However, it also brings a range of new responsibilities and challenges to the parents that must be managed along with the pre-existing ones. Parents need to make a lot of adjustments as they gradually have to establish new routines and caregiving practices to meet the needs of the newborn (Belsky & Kelly, 1994; Cowan & Cowan, 1997). When a child is born with a disability, the family dynamic is significantly disrupted, often resulting in emotional difficulties and a reduced sense of well-being (Mello et al., 2019).

Furthermore, having a child with a developmental condition places substantial demands on parents, deeply affecting their physical, emotional, and overall well-being. The caregiving demands of parents having normally developing children will lessen over time, those parents who are raising developmentally disabled children often face ongoing responsibilities due to delayed or unmet developmental milestones (Tadema & Vlaskamp, 2009). Further, the caregivers have limited physical and emotional resources and these ongoing demands may result in a chronic depletion of parental energy (Janisse et al., 2009). Parents of children with disability often feel more stressed due to the challenges of providing constant care and concerns about their child's future (Tadema & Vlaskamp, 2009).

Further, parents spend a significant amount of money to meet their child's needs, which adds to the financial burden and increased stress. The ongoing stress due to the caregiving demands and challenges of taking care of a child with disability will result in adverse mental and physical health issues such as exhaustion, anxiety, and depression (CDC, 2010). However, when social support is lacking or inconsistent, parents may experience a diminished sense of

perceived support, leading to feelings of isolation and helplessness. The decline in experienced social support is closely linked to reduced mental health, as robust social connections serve as a vital shield against the adverse impacts of ongoing caregiving stress (Mercado, 2023).

Review of Literature

Anwar et al. (2025) investigated the link between frustration and psychological well-being among parents of children who are diagnosed with neurodevelopmental disorders. The results indicated that higher levels of frustration are linked to lower psychological health.

Shimil (2024) explored the comprehensive well-being and communal support available to mothers having children with learning disabilities. As a result, it was found that mothers of normally developing children reported higher psychological well-being as compared to their counterparts. However, there were no such differences in communal support among parents of the two groups.

Swamy et al. (2024) conducted a study to examine the psychological health and perceived stress of caregivers for children with intellectual disabilities. The findings indicated that these caregivers experience elevated levels of perceived stress and exhibit compromised psychological health.

Angeline et al. (2023) evaluated the impact of parenting stress on mental wellness. The findings revealed a negative correlation between parenting stress and mental wellness among mothers of children with ADHD.

Kachroo et al. (2023) assessed the quality of life and overall psychological wellness among mothers of children with multiple disabilities. The results showed that 31% of the mothers reported a poor quality of life and only 5% rated it as good. Furthermore, it was also found that mothers of children with physical disabilities reported poor quality of life and lower psychological wellness compared to mothers of typically developing children.

Poonam (2022) examined the family burden, social support, and mental well-being among parents of children diagnosed with autism. Findings revealed that parents of children with autism reported higher levels of family burden, lower social support and

Author Note

¹Kavita Thapa, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology, M.B Govt.P. G College, Haldwani, Kumaun University, Nainital

²Anu Sharma, Special Educator, D.A.V Public School, Sector-10A Gurugram, Haryana

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Kavita Thapa, Research Scholar, Department of Psychology, M.B Govt.P. G College, Haldwani, Kumaun University, Nainital
E-mail: kavithapa10@gmail.com

lower mental well-being as compared to parents of typically developing children.

Hussein et al. (2021) evaluated the perceived social support and psychological well-being among mothers of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in Iraq. The findings revealed that the majority of mothers reported moderate to high levels of perceived social support. Further, the majority of mothers indicated a moderate level of psychological well-being.

Kumari et al. (2020) explored the psychological wellness and available social support among mothers of differently abled children. The analysis of the result indicated that there is no difference in available social support between the two groups. However, mothers of children with intellectual disabilities exhibited poorer psychological wellness compared to mothers of typically developing children.

Kuru et al. (2018) investigated available social support and quality of life among parents of children with autism. The findings revealed that parents of children with autism reported above-average levels of available social support and average quality of life. Additionally, mothers experienced a lower quality of life compared to fathers.

Objectives of the Study

- To evaluate the perceived social support accessible to parents of children with developmental differences in comparison to parents of children with standard development.
- To investigate the psychological well-being of parents of children with developmental differences compared to parents of children with standard development.
- To explore the connection between perceived social support and psychological well-being among parents of children with developmental differences compared to parents of children with standard development.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There will be a notable difference in perceived social support available to parents of children with developmental differences compared to parents of children with standard development.
- A notable difference will be evident in the psychological well-being of parents of children with developmental differences compared to parents of children with standard development.
- A relationship will be found between perceived social support and psychological well-being among parents of children with developmental differences and parents of children with standard development.

Method

Participants

A total of 76 parents were selected from the Delhi-NCR region, divided equally into two groups: 38 parents of children with developmental differences and 38 parents of children with standard development.

Variable

In this study, the independent variable is the parent group category, consisting of parents of children with developmental differences and parents of children with standard development. The dependent variables are perceived social support and psychological well-being.

Participant Selection Criteria

The inclusion criteria for the study required participants to be parents aged 22 to 55 years, irrespective of whether they were the mother or the father. The study included only those parents who agreed to participate on a voluntary basis. Participants were excluded if they had any diagnosed mental or physical illness or if they chose not to participate in the study.

Measures

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS): This scale was created by Zimet et al. (1988). It is a self-report measure comprised of 12 items, which are scored on a seven-point Likert scale, from "Very strongly disagree" (1) to "Very strongly agree" (7). The higher the scores, the greater the perceived social support. The scale demonstrated strong internal consistency, having a reliability coefficient of .88, and good construct validity.

Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale: It was developed by Ryff and Keyes in 1995. This questionnaire consists of 18 items, which are scored on a seven-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." The scale has good internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha ranging from .60 to .78, and shows good construct validity.

Procedure

To start the data collection process, the researcher first identified and reached out to individuals and institutions that serve children with special needs. Before initiating the study, written consent was obtained from the head of the respective organizations. The research purpose and significance were made clear to the participants. They were further given clear instructions on how to fill the questionnaire. Furthermore, they were informed that their information would be kept confidential.

Statistical Analysis

For data analysis, SPSS was used to find out the mean, standard deviation, t-test and correlation.

Results

Table 1

Mean, SD and t-values of Perceived Social Support among Two Groups of Parents

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t
Parents of children with developmental differences	38	61.84	14.15	2.97*
Parents of children with standard development	38	69.45	06.90	

Note. *Significant at $p < .05$

The result in Table 1 shows that parents of children with developmental differences reported lower levels of perceived social support ($M = 61.84$, $SD = 14.15$) compared to parents of children with standard development ($M = 69.45$, $SD = 6.90$). The difference between the two groups was statistically significant ($t = 2.97$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 2 illustrates the psychological well-being among parents of children with developmental differences and parents of children with standard development. The result discloses a notable

Table 2

Mean, SD, and t-value of Psychological Well-being between Parents Group

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t
Parents of children with developmental differences	38	83.50	11.85	2.53*
Parents of children with standard development	38	90.39	11.90	

Note. *Significant at $p < .05$

disparity between these two groups. For parents of children with developmental differences, the mean is 83.50 and standard deviation is 11.85. While for parents of children with standard development, the mean and standard deviation are 90.39 and 11.90, respectively. A t-value of 2.53 indicates statistical significance at level 0.05.

Table 3

Correlation of Perceived Social Support and Psychological Well-being among Parents

Variables	Perceived Social Support	Psychological well-being
Perceived Social Support	1	0.317*
Psychological well-being	0.317*	1

Note. *Significant at $p < .005$

Table 3 indicates a positive relationship between perceived social support and psychological well-being among parents of children with developmental differences and parents of children with standard development.

Discussion

Parenting a child with a developmental disability involves navigating numerous challenges, including managing regular hospital visits, therapy sessions, and addressing individualized educational requirements, while also facing societal stigma, discrimination, and reduced social support (Gray, 2002; Broady et al., 2017). These factors can lead to higher levels of caregiving burden, limited opportunities for social engagement, and negatively impact their psychological well-being. Hence, a comparative study was conducted to investigate perceived social support and psychological well-being among parents of children with developmental differences and parents of children with standard development. The results indicated a notable difference in perceived social support among the two groups of parents. This difference may be explained by the fact that these parents experience social stigma, marginalization, and limited social interaction opportunities due to the disability of their child. Further, these difficulties lead to feelings of guilt, social isolation, and limited access to support networks among parents of children with developmental disabilities (Shahali et al., 2024).

Additionally, the results showed a notable difference in psychological well-being between parents of children with developmental differences and those of typically developing children. Our finding is consistent with Shimil (2024) who reported that mothers of normally developing children exhibited better psychological health as compared to mothers of children with developmental disabilities. Similarly, Boromand et al. (2014) identified a significant difference in psychological health between parents of children with intellectual disabilities and those of

normally developing children.

In addition, the present study identified a positive correlation between perceived social support and psychological well-being in both groups of parents. These results are in agreement with the findings of Kumari et al. (2020) who also reported a positive relationship between perceived social support and psychological well-being among parents of children with intellectual disabilities.

Conclusion

The analysis of the study revealed that there is a notable difference in perceived social support and psychological well-being among parents of children with developmental differences and parents of children with standard development. Furthermore, there was a positive correlation between perceived social support and psychological health in both groups.

References

- Angeline, J., & Rathnasabapathy, M. (2023). Role of perceived social support in the relationship between parenting stress and psychological well-being of Mothers of children with ADHD: A mediation model. *Universal Journal of Public Health, 11*(6), 838-844. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujph.2023.110607>
- Anwar, P., Panhwar, M., Sindhu, Z. M., Bibi, F., & Ain, S. F. U. (2025). Frustration and psychological well-being in parents of children with neurodevelopmental disorders. *Journal of Regional Studies Review, 4*(1), 223-228. <https://doi.org/10.62843/jrsr/2025>.
- Autism & Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network Surveillance Year 2008 Principal Investigators, & Centers for Disease Control & Prevention (2012). Prevalence of autism spectrum disorders-autism and developmental disabilities monitoring network, 14 sites, united states, 2008. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report. Surveillance Summaries (Washington, D. C.: 2002), 61*(3), 1-19.
- Belsky, J., & Kelly, J. (1994). *The transition to parenthood*. New York: Delacorte.
- Boromand, N., Narimani, M., & Mosazadeh, T. (2014). Comparing the psychological well-being factors among the parents of the mentally retarded children with those of the normal children. *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences (ILSHS), 21*, 1-8.
- Broady, T. R., Stoyles, G. J., & Morse, C. (2017). Understanding carers' lived experience of stigma: The voice of families with a child on the autism spectrum. *Health and Social Care in the Community, 25*(1), 224-233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hsc.12297>
- Chand, P. (2021). Family burden, social support and general well-being among parents of children with autism. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research, 11*(1(1)), 88-97. <http://ijmer.in.doi./2022/11.01.14>
- Cowan, C. P., & Cowan, P. A. (1997). Becoming a parent. In A. S. Skolnick and J. H. Skolnick. *Family in transition* (pp. 201-213). New York: Longman.
- Gray, D.E. (2002). Everybody just freezes. Everybody is just embarrassed: Felt and enacted stigma among parents of children with high functioning autism'. *Sociology of Health and Illness, 24*(6), 734-749. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.00316>
- Gull, M., & Nizam, N. (2015). Comparative study of hope and psychological well-being among the parents of physically and intellectually disabled children. *International Journal of Modern Social Sciences, 4*(2), 143-152.
- Hussein, A. N., & Mohammed, Q. Q. (2021). Perceived social support and psychological well-being among mothers of children with autism spectrum disorder in Al-Nasiriyah city. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 25*(4), 10117-10126.
- Janisse, H.C., Barnett, D., & Nies, M.A. (2009). Perceived energy for parenting: A new conceptualization and scale. *Journal of Child and Family Studies, 18*, 312-322.
- Kachroo, W. Q., Reshi, I. A., & War, M. I. (2023). Quality of life and psychological well-being among mothers having children with multiple disabilities. *International Journal of Economic, Business, Accounting, Agriculture Management and Sharia Administration, 3*(1), 217-221.
- Kumari, S., & Kiran, M. (2020). Parenting stress, psychological well-being and social support in mothers of children with mental retardation. *International Journal of Scientific Research, 9*(1), 57-60. <https://doi.org/10.36106/ijsr>.
- Kumari, S., Kumar, V., & Kiran, M. (2020). Psychological Well-Being and Perceived Social Support in Mother of differently abled Children: A Comparative study. *Indian Journal of Health Social Work, 2*(1), 24-29.
- Kuru, N., & Piyal, B. (2018). Perceived social support and quality of life of parents of children with autism. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice, 21*(9), 1182-1189. https://doi.org/10.4103/njcp.njcp_13_18

- Lovell, B., & Wetherell, M. A. (2019). Affiliate stigma, perceived social support and perceived stress in caregivers of children with autism spectrum disorder: A multiple mediation study. *Archives of Psychiatric Nursing*, 33(5), 31-35.
- Mello, C., Rivard, M., Terroux, A., & Mercier, C. (2019). Quality of life in families of young children with autism spectrum disorder. *American Journal on Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities*, 124(6), 535-548. <https://doi.org/10.1352/1944-7558-124.6.535>
- Parameswari, S., & Eljo, J. O. J. G. (2017). Psychological well-being among the parents of children with intellectual and developmental disabilities. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4, 08-12.
- Shahali, S., Tavousi, M., Sadighi, J., Kermani, R. M., & Rostami, R. (2024). Health challenges faced by parents of children with disabilities: A scoping review. *BMC Pediatrics*, 24(1), 6-19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12887-024-05104-3>
- Shimil, P.V. (2024). Perceived social support and psychological well-being and in mothers of learning-disabled children: A comparative study. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 12(2), 556-563. <https://doi.org/10.25215/1202.055>
- Swamy, I.C., Kumar, G.V., & Manjunatha, M.C. (2024, April) *Perceived stress and psychological well-being of caretakers of children with Intellectual Disability* [paper presentation]. Rethinking the idea of Disability: People, Paradigms and Prototypes, Mysuru, Karnataka, India.
- Tadema, A.C., & Vlaskamp, C. (2009). The time and effort in taking care for children with profound intellectual and multiple disabilities: A study on care load and support. *British Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 38, 41-48.

Received February 1, 2026

Revision received March 5, 2026

Accepted March 8, 2026